

Progressive damage in stitched composites: Static tensile tests and tension-tension fatigue

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ABSTRACT

The paper describes progressive damage in static tensile tests and tension-tension fatigue in structurally stitched carbon/epoxy NCF composites, in comparison with their non-stitched counterparts. Analogies between damage development in quasi-static tension and tension-tension fatigue are analyzed and links between the damage initiation thresholds in quasi-static tests and fatigue life are established.

Keywords: Textile Composite; Structural Stitching; Experimental Characterization; Stitched Reinforcements; Fatigue; Damage; Non-crimp Fabrics

1. INTRODUCTION

In this study, experimental data are presented for typically structurally stitched multilayer preform, composed of a carbon-fiber non-crimp fabric (NCF) and impregnated with an epoxy resin. The term “structural” here means that the stitching yarn does not only consolidate the plies, but constitutes also a through-the-thickness reinforcement. One stitching technique – tufting – is studied, with 67 tex carbon yarn and several stitching legths for the quasi-static investigation and in one configuration for the tensile-tensile fatigue study. The fatigue behavior investigation is conducted in order to analyze the differences in the response of structurally stitched NCF and non-structurally stitched preforms. This study involves tensile-tensile fatigue tests, damage observation and post-fatigue tensile tests with analysis of remaining developing damage.

2. MATERIALS

0°/90° and ±45° Saertex[®] NCFs having the areal weight of 556 and 540 g/m² respectively are used as the raw materials. “0°” here corresponds to the machine direction of the non-structural stitching (for i.e. the horizontal direction in *fig. 1*). The areal weight of ±45° and 90° plies is 267 g/m², while 0° ply weights 283 g/m². The carbon fiber bundles are knit together with a thin thermoplastic yarn (7.4 tex, 2.6x5 mm tricot + chain knitting pattern, 6 g/m²). The preform is composed of 6 layers in a symmetric stacking sequence [45/-45/0/90/45/-45]_s.

Fig 1. Tufting appearance and size on the structurally stitched material (B_0 varies for quasi-static tests). From left: face view, back view, 3D scheme

For the structural stitching, 1 K carbon rowing and tufting method (KL RS 522 stitching head mounted on a KUKA-robot) are employed, with square piercing pattern 5x5, 7x7, or 9x9 mm. The stitching direction coincides with the 0° direction of the preform. For tension-tension fatigue tests only 5x5 mm pattern is employed. Composite plates (stitched and non-stitched) are produced by means of VAP (Vacuum Assisted Process) technology, using RTM-6 epoxy resin. The final thickness is 3.2-3.5 mm that gives the average fiber volume fraction in the composite (V_f) of 63%. The material properties are listed in *table 1*.

	Material	Fiber \varnothing , [μm]	Twist, t/m	Density, g/cm^3	Lin. dens. [tex]	E, [GPa]	ν	σ_{ult} [MPa]
Carbon fibres in the ply	Tenax HTS 5631	7	n/a	1.77	n/a	240/72	0.270/0.150	4300/-
Non-structural stitch	PES 76/24/1	2	Z24	1.38	7.4	2.7	0.3	72
Structural stitch	Tenax HTA 5241	7	S15	1.76	67	238/14	0.230/0.014	3950/-
Resin	HexFlow RTM-6	n/a	n/a	1.14	n/a	2.89	0.26	75

Table 1. Properties of the composite constituents (longitudinal / transversal)

3. QUASI-STATIC TENSION

The tensile tests are performed according to ASTM D3039; 250 mm long specimens having a constant (3.2-3.5)x30 mm cross-section and 60 mm long end tabs are used. Series of 6 (unstitched) or 8 (stitched) are tested for 0° (along the structural stitching) and 90° directions, at the cross-head displacement rate of 3 mm/min. The tests are monitored with the acoustic emission (AE) and full-field strain registration.

The latter one is used to register as local strain distribution, as well as to measure the average strain in the specimen (optical extensometer). All the strains reported here for quasi-static tests are measured in this way. First, four specimens in a series (two for unstitched) are tested until failure. Here since the AE sensors should be removed before the specimens failure, the loading is not completely monotonical but is paused at a certain load level. Two other specimens are tested

until the “mass crack onset” level (ϵ_2). The specimens are further inspected with X-rays to reveal the damage development features.

3.1 Stiffness and strength

Table 2 shows the measured Young’s moduli and Poisson’s ratios. In all the cases 90° direction is slightly stiffer than 0° one. For the Poisson’s ratio there is the same trend: tension in 90° usually gives slightly larger mean values, although the standard deviation overlaps the difference. Increased stitching density (9, 7, 5 mm) is not accompanied by increased stiffness in 0° direction, moreover, a certain decreasing trend is evident. This can be explained by the fact that the stiffness added by horizontal yarn patches is compensated by distorted fiber orientation (due to openings). The general conclusion is that the structural stitching has a minor effect on the in-plane stiffness parameters.

The material exhibits a gradually decreasing stiffness (about 40% decrease till the final failure). This should mainly be explained by crack formation and nonlinear matrix deformation.

stitching	E_0	E_{90}	E_z	$\nu_{0,90}$	$\nu_{90,0}$	$\nu_{z,0} (\nu_{z,90})$
n/a	39.3±2.5	41.4±1.6	15.6±3.2	.45±.08	.56±.08	.023±.012
9×9 mm	39.7±2.6	41.1±3.2	16.6±4.9	.43±.09	.51±.17	.051±.021
7×7 mm	39.4±3.0	41.6±2.7	19.1±3.4	.44±.13	.54±.10	.038±.022
5×5 mm	38.9±1.7	40.1±2.1	–	.48±.07	.53±.12	–
5×5 mm short	38.1±1.7	40.2±2.0	14.5±3.4	.50±.12	.48±.06	.039±.015

stitching	$\epsilon_1, \%$	$\epsilon_2, \%$	$\epsilon^{ult}, \%$	σ^{ult}, MPa
n/a	.16±.10/.13±.10	.57±.05/.45±.09	1.17±.14/1.43±.04	432.6±14.9/390.1±0.7
9×9	.11±.06/.12±.08	.39±.07/.36±.06	1.42±.13/1.40±.09	472.7±21.8/440.6±25.3
7×7	.08±.04/.10±.05	.31±0.06/.25±.02	1.41±.09/1.44±.08	493.0±20.0/457.3±12.9
5×5	.12±.04/.08±.04	.26±.06/.22±.06	1.51±.02/1.52±.04	493.1±15.3/478.3±6.5
5×5 short	.13±.04/.11±.04	.28±.04/.27±.09	1.49±.07/1.49±.09	473.0±5.7/478.1±13.8

Table 2. Stiffness and strength. The moduli are given in GPa; strength data shown for loading directions 0°/90°.

Table 2 summarizes also the measured ultimate strains and stresses. It is seen that the structural stitching increases the ultimate load; however this is less prominent for denser stitching (5x5 mm) than for the spaced one (9x9 mm). Extensive delamination occurs in the unstitched composite, when outer ±45° layers lose bonding with inner 90° layers and then naturally become more compliant in tension.

3.2 Damage development

It is seen in DIC images that that the tufting causes prominent strain concentration at the stitching sites, although the backside gives some blurred pattern, probably due to yarn loops. But not all the sites show such a growth in strain, thus it can be suggested that damage gradually accumulates at selected (having unfavorable strength) stitching sites. Only outer ±45° layers are

available for optical measurements hence 0/90° layers (responsible for the final failure) may have other strain patterns.

Figure 2. Definition of the average characteristic strains ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 using AE data for conventional crack energy (left) or number of events (right). 5x5 mm tufted specimens, 0° loading. Values of ϵ_2 for different specimens are marked with filled dots.

Figure 2 shows examples of the cumulative AE energy and cumulative AE event count. The damage onset is detected already at the beginning of the test (at about 0.05%-0.15% strain), when a few low energy occur with low frequency. The corresponding strain level is further denoted as ϵ_1 and can be attributed to initiation of new cracks in the weakest locations. At a certain moment the frequency increases, both the energy content and event count rise quickly, and the specimen starts to emit popping sounds indicating extensive appearance of relatively large cracks, presumably in the off-axes plies. This is called “mass crack formation”, and the corresponding strain level is denoted as ϵ_2 .

The X-ray images reveal clearly that the cracks are near the stitching sites; this occurs even due to the non-structural stitching, while the tufting provokes even larger cluster of cracks. The clusters are mainly confined in the plies orientated in $\pm 45^\circ$ to the loading direction, although relatively rare cracks appear in 0/90° plies also. This material degradation mechanism is in contrast with the assumption that the cracks should first appear in the plies transversely oriented to the load direction. It is seen also that the non-stitched composite, does not show such almost continuous cracks as is occurs in the structurally stitched one.

4. TENSION-TENSION FATIGUE

A series of tensile-tensile fatigue tests until failure has been performed in order to generate a S-N curve, a series of tensile-tensile fatigue tests with fixed number of cycles were intended for damage analysis (through X-Ray observation) then post fatigue tensile tests.

250 mm long specimens were used according to ASTM D3039, with a constant (3.2-3.5)x24 mm cross-section and 50 mm long aluminum end tabs. Series of 3 specimens in each category (structurally stitched and non-structurally stitched), stress levels and direction (0° and 90°) are tested at a 4 Hz frequency (except the lowest 200 MPa stress level performed at 10 Hz) with a sinusoidal load variation in time with the ratio $R = \sigma_{\min} / \sigma_{\max} = 0.1$.

4.1 S-N Curves and fatigue limits

Fig. 3. S-N curves (horizontal axis: number of cycles to failure, vertical axis: maximum stress) for structurally stitched material (left column) and non-structurally stitched (right column); 0° direction top row, 90° bottom row. Arrows indicate stopped test at 2 million cycles or above.

Fig. 3 shows the fatigue limits for each category of material and load direction compared with the other types of specimens and their trendlines. The stress values for one cycle (on the vertical axis) correspond to the static strength. Due to lower ultimate stress of the unstitched material the 400 MPa level as σ_{\max} in fatigue testing has been avoided.

The 2 million cycles were been considered as indication of “infinite life”, and the tests were stopped at that time. According to this assumption, the structurally stitched material in 0° direction and the non-structurally stitched one in 90° reached infinite life at $\sigma_{\max}=240$ MPa; the others at 200 MPa. Therefore the fatigue limit appears to be higher than the damage initiation level recorded during static behavior investigation.

The response of the unstitched material is rather worse in terms of number of cycles at failure considering the same stress level, especially in 0° direction at high stress level. In 90° direction tests the difference is minor.

3.2 Fatigue tests: a short gallery

Fig. 4 illustrates the progression of the fatigue tests. The displacement referred to in this figure is the displacement of the grips.

It appears that the external $\pm 45^\circ$ layers of all the samples are usually delaminated early: the phenomenon occurs at variable number of cycles according to the load and is usually connected to a stiffness drop and is more relevant on the non-structurally stitched material. Studies on the static behavior revealed that the structural stitching may prevent the spreading of macro delaminations specially on the 5x5 mm stitching configuration and in 90° test direction. A similar effect on the shape of the failed specimens has been observed also during fatigue (*fig. 5*).

Fig. 4. Fatigue tests, Load vs. Displacement diagrams. Left: non-structurally stitched 0° at 240 MPa with failure at about 650,000 cycles; right: non-structurally stitched 90° at 240 MPa without failure after 2 million cycles.

Fig. 5. Side view of broken specimens tested in 90° direction: a: structurally stitched; b: non-structurally stitched.

Damage observation through X-Ray (see *fig 6* and *fig 7*) has been done after fatigue tests with fixed number of cycles, for both stitched and non-stitched specimens: 1,000, 10,000 and 100,000 cycles. The stress level σ_{\max} was set to 240 MPa. The most visible cracks are in the $\pm 45^\circ$ direction both at 1,000 cycles as well as 100,000. Visible delaminations (without complete failure though) were observed on some unstitched specimens in 90° direction as shown by black zones in the captured pictures.

3.3 Post-fatigue tensile tests

Specimens tested at controlled number of fatigue cycles are then tested under static load according to ASTM D3039. Both 0° and 90° direction are tested at the cross-head displacement rate of 2 mm/min. When possible (good condition of the surface and absence of macro delaminations after tensile-tensile fatigue) tests are monitored with the acoustic emission (AE) and full-field strain registration. This strain mapping is used to register the average strain in the specimen as an optical extensometer.

Fig. 6. X-ray images, structurally stitched material: from left: after 1,000; 10,000 and 100,000 cycles.

Fig 7 X-ray images, non-structurally stitched material: From left: after 1,000; 10,000 and 100,000 cycles.

Since the AE sensors should be removed before the specimen failure, the loading is not completely monotonical but is paused at a certain load level which is usually around the former corresponding σ_{\max} stress level used for the tensile-tensile fatigue pre-X-Ray testing.

These post-fatigue tests allow also determining Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, ultimate stress σ_{ult} and strain ϵ_{ult} (Table 3).

Stitching	E_0 , [GPa]	E_{90} , [GPa]	$\nu_{0,90}$	$\nu_{90,0}$	$\sigma_{\text{ult},0}$, [MPa]	$\sigma_{\text{ult},90}$, [MPa]	$\epsilon_{\text{ult},0}$, [%]	$\epsilon_{\text{ult},90}$, [%]
no stitching, 10,000 cyc.	36.6±1.3	43.2±3.4	.45±.14	.57±.09	452±6.4	444±29.0	1.49±.16	1.36±.07
5x5 mm, 100,000 cyc.	38.4±3.1	41.0±1.4	.48±.11	.58±.11	434±26.3	462±26.0	1.30±.07	1.37±.09

Table 3. Post-fatigue tests: stiffness properties and strength properties

Many of the non-stitched specimens tested up to 100,000 cycles, were not processed in the post-fatigue tests with AE recording and full-field strain registration because of the heavy damages on them after the fatigue session, hence the data for this specimens is not shown in Table 3. Comparing the data with the stiffness and strength of “virgin” specimens (Table 2), a significant drop of the properties is seen for testing in 0° direction: by 33% in E_0 , 40% in σ_0 . Interestingly, there is no statistically significant change of stiffness and strength for the samples tested in 90° direction. All the results show a 90° direction as rather stiffer than 0° direction, although the standard deviation makes the difference quite similar to the one recorded during quasi-static

investigation study. As concluded in quasi-static study section, the structural stitching has a minor effect on the stiffness (slight positive in 0°, almost negligible negative effect in 90°), but the high damage generally observed in non-structurally stitched specimens after 100,000 cycles, makes the results of the 5x5 mm stitched material more reliable.

Ultimate stresses and strains are also shown in *Table 3*. Apparently the structural stitching increases the ultimate stress only in 90° direction, but considering the stiffness/strength dropping of the non-structurally stitched material mentioned above, a general higher value of the strength is believed to be due to the structural stitching. It can be assumed that the ±45° layers debonding, which usually occurs in early cycles for the non-stitched material, has major consequences on the properties. No significant difference of the Poisson’s ratio has been observed between the specimen types.

A typical load curve and recording of AE emissions during the test for a fatigued specimen are shown in *fig. 8*. The material does not exhibit a significant stiffness drop as in static tests on non-fatigued specimens. This is probably due to the fact that the most part of the damages due to the fatigue load range have already occurred and the behavior is rather stable during the post-fatigue tension.

Figure 8. Post-fatigue tensile test, stitched specimen, 90°: typical load curve (left), AE recorded events and cumulative energy (right).

Specimen type	σ_{max} , [MPa]*	ϵ_{max} , [%]*	$\sigma_{threshold}$, [MPa]	$\epsilon_{threshold}$, [%]
(no stitching), 0° direction	240	0.6	225±12	.75±.10
(no stitching), 90° direction	240	0.6	231±3	.58±.04
5x5 mm, 0° direction	240	0.6	242±6	.69±.07
5x5 mm, 90° direction	240	0.6	239±3	.63±.01

Table 4. Severe damage initiation thresholds on fatigued specimens. *Maximum strain values in the fatigue tests are calculated using 40 GPa modulus.

Is also noticeable how the fatigue threshold is matched with the AE recording: the major amount of events recorded in AE start occurring around the stress formerly set during fatigue tests (240 MPa). From the very beginning of the load increasing to the threshold level, very few events are recorded in the low-stress area, then a rather void zone is detected till the threshold value of stress set during fatigue treatment. At that threshold level the frequency of events increases dramatically in every test and the specimens start also emitting noisy cracking sounds, probably indicating

fibre ruptures. The cracking continues almost constantly till the sensors are detached from the specimen. Averaged $\epsilon_{\text{threshold}}$ strains are shown in *Table 4*, these values are determined by the correspondence zone of a large increase of the number of events. At this level it seems that the fracture energy becomes enough to provoke more cracks and damages.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper deals with an experimental characterization of the quasi static tensile behavior and the fatigue behavior of a non-crimp structurally stitched carbon/epoxy composite vs. the unstitched composites. The main conclusions are:

- The structural stitching yarns and induced by them distortions of the fibres in the plies produce negligible influence on the in-plane components of the homogenized stiffness;
- The stitching sites can play a role of stress concentrators and trigger damage (higher stitching density results in earlier damage onset) but the general effect can be positive. E.g. in the present case, the acoustic emission reveals that the tufted specimens show larger crack energy index and event count under moderate load than the unstitched specimens. On the contrary, under higher loads both criteria indicate lower crack development in the tufted specimens;
- Considering an “infinite fatigue life” as a survival at 2 million cycles, the structurally stitched material loaded in 0° direction (according to the non-structural stitching direction) exhibits infinite life at the fatigue load of 240 MPa (σ_{max} , with $R=0.1$) as well as the unstitched material loaded in 90° . The stitched material loaded in 90° and the unstitched material loaded in 0° have shown a lower infinite life level (200 MPa) or anyway a diffused damage at 240 MPa close to 2 million cycles;
- For the both stitched and unstitched material, the fatigue limits are much higher than the damage initiation levels reported after the static studies;
- The response of the unstitched material is generally worse than the stitched, although the difference is decreasing with lower stress levels till a probable overlapping in the trend lines above 2 million cycles;
- The $\pm 45^\circ$ external layers are subjected to early delamination during fatigue tests and the phenomenon is more harsh on the non-structurally stitched material. After that the response and the stiffness is belived to be stabilized till failure. The presence of the structural stitching usually prevents the macro-delamination in the specimens;
- Up to 100,000 cycles, mainly cracks in the $\pm 45^\circ$ direction are visible using X-Ray observation. Huge delamination may occur on unstitched material specially in 90° direction;
- Post-fatigue tests showed that only unstitched material with diffused damages after 100,000 cycles revealed a substantial difference in stiffness and strength from the static tests; same situation regarding the ultimate stress of the non-stitched. No significant differences were observed for the stitched material.
- AE data recorded during tension on fatigued specimens, show a limited number of AE events up to the load corresponding to the maximum stress in the fatigue loading. When the maximum stress in the fatigue loading is reached, the cracking is re-started.

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